

FHERITALE WHITE PAPER

KEY SELECTED PRIORITIES

Micro and Nanoparticles Research: Priorities, Challenges and Recommendations

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1. Introduction

FHERITALE goal is preparing a roadmap for services to address the needs of research to investigate the impact on health and on the environment that a set of selected, prioritized artificial materials can have. Given the interdisciplinary nature of this research area, these services will span several domains, from health, food and environmental sciences. The goal of this document is to gather a first set of priorities, challenges, and recommendations that have emerged from the activities carried out so far in the frame of the FHERITALE coordination action.

2. Background

Human activities, particularly industrialization and the widespread use of artificial materials, have significantly affected human, animal, and environmental health. These impacts have become increasingly urgent as industrial processes continue to accelerate. A key consequence is the massive waste generation, with the European Union alone producing 2,233 million tonnes of waste in 2022, highlighting the scale of human influence on the environment¹. This waste contributes to pollution and worsens interconnected health issues, stressing the need for urgent action to address environmental degradation. Despite growing research on such environmental and health impacts, knowledge gaps persist, partly due to a lack of standard definitions and measurement protocols. To understand the extent of these challenges, a "One Health"² approach is critical.

The FHERITALE project aims to highlight these gaps by analyzing current literature on artificial materials at the nano and microscale within the One Health framework. This includes identifying trends, clusters, and technological gaps and making it possible through technological developments within research infrastructures to close such gaps.

During the first fifteen months of the FHERITALE project, several networking activities were carried out with the following aims:

- 1) providing an overview of the research currently addressing the impact on health of artificial micro- and nano-particles
- 2) providing the European research community with a comprehensive cross-thematic landscape of available services for a set of scientific priorities

¹ [Eurostat Statistics](#)

² "One Health" is defined by the OHHLEP ([One Health High-Level Expert Panel](#)) as an integrated, unifying approach that aims to sustainably balance and optimise the health of people, animals, and ecosystems ([One Health Overview](#))

These activities, also leveraging on the contribution of the external experts (their institutions are listed in the table reported in the Appendix), resulted in:

- A **bibliometric study**, supporting the mapping of the current research landscape over the past five years for these priorities, has been completed and is pending publication
- 2 days of “**brainstorming groups retreat**” with representatives of European RIs and external expert organized in Utrecht (MS4.2: “Strategic Meeting Retreat”)
- A **first map of services** currently available in relevant European Research Infrastructures (RIs) (Appendix; MS3.1 available in the website: [link](#))

One aspect that has been revealed by the bibliometric study is about the usage of technologies. We found that Microscopy techniques are widely used, whereas other approaches have a marginal utilization. It is quite likely that this gap can be ascribed, at least in part, to steep cost and difficulty of maintenance of specialized instruments. RIs have a key role in promoting and enhancing the usage of cutting-edge instrumentation. Furthermore, collaborative efforts between RIs on technological aspects might lead to the development of innovative equipment and novel protocols beneficial to the entire community of current and potential new users engaged in the study of micro and nanoparticles.

3. Priorities

The following **thematic priorities** have been defined based on the expertise of the FHERITALE partners and shared within the project consortium (MS4.1):

- Micro and nanoplastics (MNPs)
- Bioplastics
- Plastic additives
- Metals/Metal oxides

Starting from the four selected priorities, the discussion led to the identification of several priorities, which are summarized here:

- Understanding of the biological activity of materials
- Overall dynamics of artificial material along their lifetime from production to degradation or absorption
- Risk assessment: conduct comprehensive risk assessments to evaluate the potential hazards and risks of nanoplastic exposure to human health and the environment
- Mitigation and remediation: develop strategies and new innovative technologies to reduce the release of micro and nanoparticles
- Socio-economic aspects
- Impact on policies and regulations

4. Challenges and gaps

Research Gaps and Solutions:

- **Terminology:** This research field is intrinsically multidisciplinary. This raises a cogent need to have a shared terminology and vocabulary.
- **Mitigation, bioremediation, and practical applications:** while many researchers are focused on methodologies for analysis, there are fewer efforts directed toward finding solutions, particularly in terms of mitigation, bioremediation, and practical applications.
- **More flexible and comprehensive approach to nanoparticle research:** moving beyond size limits to consider the material's nature, environmental behavior, and aggregation potential. While technical challenges remain in nanoparticle measurement, especially in complex matrices, ongoing advancements in analytical techniques and regulatory perspectives will be critical for future studies. The need to address the interactions between micro- and nanoparticles across different matrices and ecosystems. Despite growing interest in nano-scale particles, particularly in health and toxicology, more research efforts are required to fully address this size range.
- **Environmental-Human Testing Gap:** there is a gap in environmental and human testing, specifically focusing on bioactive particles, which are typically the smallest particles and include various additives. This highlights the need for better instrumentation to measure these particles and call for the regulation of these emerging contaminants.
- **Risk Assessment:** Particularly critical in the food sector, where the impact of nanoparticles on human health and safety must be better understood.

Analytical Challenges:

- A significant gap is the **lack of standardized samples and methodologies** across laboratories. This issue is closely tied to the need for quality control in measuring nanoplastics and their impact. Participants emphasized the necessity of developing reference materials and validation protocols to ensure consistent results across research efforts.
- **Contamination in Testing** : data from human studies are often subject to secondary contamination, making it difficult to draw accurate conclusions.
- **Nanoplastic Detection** : there is a lack of risk assessment reviews specifically for nanoplastics, and many studies focus on the physical characterization of materials in controlled environments, which do not accurately reflect real-world conditions.
- **Reference Materials:** the need for reference materials with suitable markers or labels to measure nanoplastics in biological matrices was emphasized. These materials should cover a range of sizes and applications, not just focus on specific sizes.

Technological Gaps, Training and Collaborations:

- **Technological Development:** while microplastic characterization is relatively advanced, the technology for detecting and analyzing nanoplastics is still underdeveloped. Non-destructive methods and more robust analytical quantitative tools are needed. There is a profound need for computational modelling tools for a more complete understanding of exposure scenarios.
- **Training:** there is a significant need for training on the proper use of analytical methods and the interpretation of data, as well as on the definition of artificial materials and their impact within the OneHealth framework.
- **Collaborations:** collaboration with other projects should be encouraged in order to foster innovation and strengthen efforts towards shared goals.
- **Financial Resources:** securing adequate funding for comprehensive research. This influences research funding and focus, leading to disproportionate attention in certain areas, especially regarding costs.

Regulatory and Policy Considerations:

Key regulatory challenges include:

- Development of a shared language for better communication among stakeholders.
- Addressing homogeneity in sizes, shapes, and pollutant compositions.
- Establishing standards and standardized procedures.
- Specifying acceptable levels of variability in assessments.
- Improving detection methods and hazard surveillance.
- Enhancing public awareness regarding risks and opportunities.
- Addressing the interface with emerging nanotechnologies and biotechnologies.

Regulatory Framework:

- The Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) has research programs focused on toxicity and bioaccumulation.
- The European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) and European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) handle safety assessments, differentiating between food and cosmetic regulations.
- Ensuring that technological advancements do not exacerbate inequalities or undermine individual autonomy is vital, emphasizing stakeholder consultation.

Global Regulatory Perspectives:

- There are significant differences between national/EU regulations and those of other countries, which can create competitive imbalances.
- Historical regulatory failures underline the need for collaborative global frameworks.

5. Recommendations

Short term:

1. Develop an integrated set of services among RIs to develop services that enable interdisciplinary research on artificial materials following a One Health approach. The existing services across RIs can already fill a large part of research needs.
2. Standardization, characterization and classification of the impact of artificial material along several dimensions (toxicity for humans, plants, activity, food...) should be a priority. This is a condition for the development of policies and methods that can address the needs of industry, food production, air quality management, etc.
3. Modelling and experimental approaches that link hazard, risk, and vulnerability for artificial material, and their dynamics within the biosphere (including the whole food chain) should be developed.
4. Funding opportunities for access, training, and capacity building are needed.

Long term:

5. Active engagement with social science researchers should be sought, with the goal to understand the impact of artificial material on the society and the economy, methods to reduce the risk and vulnerability, and impact on policies. The offer of related services should be actively pursued.
6. Developing more sensitive and selective analytical methods to improve the detection and
7. quantification of nanoplastics, particularly in complex samples.
8. Establish harmonized methodologies for sampling, sample preparation, extraction, and analysis of nanoplastics in various matrices (e.g., water, soil, food, biological tissues).
9. Create and validate certified reference materials (CRMs) with varying sizes, shapes, and polymer types to ensure the accuracy and traceability of measurements.
10. Research on mitigation strategies to reduce the release of nanoplastics into the environment, including improved waste management and product design.

Appendix

Institutions, projects and initiatives of which FHERITALE external experts are representatives

Name	Type	Description
CUSP	Cluster of projects	European research cluster of projects that aims to understand the health impacts of micro and nanoplastics. https://cusp-research.eu
RIANA	INFRA-SERV	Horizon Europe-funded project that assists research in nanoscience and nanotechnology. https://riana-project.eu
Euro-Bioimaging	RI	Euro-Bioimaging nodes of U-Gent and IBA https://www.eurobioimaging.eu
NRL/ANSES	National lab	French National Reference laboratory that studies traces of artificial materials for food safety. https://www.anses
LNE	National Institution	French national laboratory of metrology and testing. https://www.lne.fr/en
INRIM	National Institution	Italian National Metrological institute. https://www.inrim.it
Trace element and nanomaterial unit of Sciensano	Research department of Sciensano	Experts in quantification, identification and characterisation of trace elements and nanoparticles with their underlying risks. https://www.sciensano.be
METROFOOD BE	RI	RI that offers high-level metrology services in food and nutrition for the enhancement of food quality and safety. https://metrofood.be
EMBRC-ERIC	RI	Marine Biology RI that offers tools for toxicogenomics services and impact of plastic pollution. https://www.embrc.eu
MUNI-RECETOX	National lab.	National laboratory that studies plastic pollution and chemical contaminants. https://www.recetox.muni.cz
UK Regulatory affairs	Expert presentation	Expert that offered insights into regulatory challenges for nano-materials.
JRC ISPRA	Nanobiosciences Unit	Experts on micro/nano-plastics and other emerging pollutants supporting EU policy. https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu
MOMENTUM	National project	Dutch project that investigates the effect of micro/nano plastics on human health, strategies for reducing exposure. https://momentummicroplastics.nl
ICAR	International institution	Global provider of independent guidelines, standards and certification for animal identification, recording and evaluation. https://www.icar.org
PLASTICHEAL	European Project	EU funded project that aims at developing innovative tools to study the impact and mode of action of micro and nanoplastics on human health. https://www.plasticheal.eu
PRIORITY - COST	Research network	Research network that aims to develop, implement, and consolidate strategies to tackle the global challenges of micro- and nanoplastics in the environment. https://ca-priority.eu
PTI+ SusPlast	RI	Interdisciplinary platform offering services for studies addressing sustainable plastics towards a circular economy. https://pti-susplast.csic.es

Map of available services. Further details about the available services can be found on the project website.

Service Type	Number of available services in this category	Research Infrastructures offering this service
Physical/chemical characterisation of Microplastics or other Microparticles	37	
Physical/chemical characterisation of Nanoplastics or other Nanoparticles	31	
Physical/chemical characterisation of Micro/Nanoparticles based on origin: Artificial, Natural, or Engineered	20	
Structural characterisation of Microplastics + other microparticles	27	
Structural characterisation of Nanoplastics + other Nanoparticles	22	
Bioplastics (biodegradable vs bio-based)	17	
Risk assessment of Micro/Nano particles	14	
Exposure assessment of Micro/Nano particles	18	
Toxicity of Micro/Nano particles	24	
Biological activity of Micro/Nano particles	24	
Monitoring of Micro/Nano particles	20	

AnaEE-ERIC	Instruct-ERIC
EIRENE-RI	METROFOOD-RI
EMBRC-ERIC	MIRRI-ERIC
EuroBioImaging-ERIC	ELIXIR

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